

Exploring the Mediating Role of Fear of Missing Out between Social Media Use and Inferiority Complex in Young Adults

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The addition of social media to most aspects of life has become unavoidable, leading to increased concerns regarding psychological well-being. Previous research linked social media use to negative self-perception, but the mechanism driving the use has not been studied much. The current study aims to explore the relationship between Social media Use, Fear of Missing Out and inferiority complex, especially to investigate the mediating role of FoMO. This study involves a quantitative, cross-sectional approach, conducted using convenience sampling from 212 adults aged between 18-30 years ($M=22.8$). The Social Media Use Scale (SMUS) developed by Tuck and Thompson (2024), Fear of Missing Out Scale (FoMOS) developed by Przybylski et al. (2013), and COMPIN-10 by Čekrljija et al. (2025) for assessing Inferiority Complex were employed for data collection from the respondents. Statistical tests employed for the study include Pearson correlation, independent sample t-test, ANOVA, and mediation analysis. The correlational analysis indicated that the relationship between social media use, FoMO, and Inferiority Complex was positive and significant. Mediation analysis indicated that FoMO partially mediated the relationship between comparison-based social media use and Inferiority Complex ($ab = 0.30$). Additionally, it was found that passive users had higher inferiority scores than balanced users ($p < .05$). There were no significant gender differences found, also it was observed that social media usage and comparison behaviours decreased with age. These findings suggest that social media use does not directly lead to inferiority, but rather FoMO and comparison-based behaviours that bring about feelings of inferiority. This research also points to the detrimental effects of passive and comparative usage of social media, thus supporting the necessity of designing strategies to reduce the impact of FoMO, as well as the usage of social media on the well-being of individuals.

Keywords: Social media use, FoMO, inferiority complex, social comparison, mediation analysis

Social media is now a constant feature of daily life, changing the way individuals communicate and develop their personal identities. If looked around, at least six out of ten individuals will be surfing through any social media apps (Kemp, 2024). In the case of India, the youth of the country spend most of their time online, where the use of digital platforms is considered the most prominent means of expressing oneself (Bala, 2014; Prajapati et al., 2020). However, the impact of these platforms on the minds of the people is not straightforward. In the context of the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT), it has been mentioned that people use these platforms as a means of fulfilling their specific needs (Joinson, 2008). However,

the ability of people to curate their profiles makes them showcase unrealistic images of themselves rather than showing the reality of their lives (Attah et al., 2022).

The most prominent reason for people feeling the need to check their social media profiles constantly is the Fear of Missing Out (FoMO). FoMO is said to be one of the most common types of anxiety that a person can experience when they feel that others are having fun or are involved in something meaningful (Przybylski et al., 2013). This has a close association with Self-Determination Theory. This theory suggests that all humans need to feel connected to others, in control of their own lives, and capable of doing things well (Ryan & Deci, 2000). If these needs aren't being met in real life, people often look for quick satisfaction through social media (Koole et al., 2018). In such a situation, FoMO serves as a kind of bridge, as the fear of being left out forces individuals to stay connected online. This, in turn, forces them to look at even more updates from their peers, which only increases their FoMO and affects their concentration and mental well-being negatively (Gupta & Sharma, 2021; Nagar, 2024).

The constant cycle of digital connection can create negative "upward social comparisons," wherein individuals tend to compare their lives with those of their peers. Studies have found that individuals who are passive users of social media are more likely to experience negative feelings of inferiority when they compare their unedited lives with the edited versions of their peers' lives (Verduyn et al., 2020; Vogel et al., 2014). While normal feelings of inferiority can sometimes function as a normal motivator for individuals to become better versions of themselves (Adler, 1927/1967) the constant pressures of the digital world can cause feelings of

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inferiority to turn into a full-scale Inferiority Complex. The latter is characterized by self-doubt and low self-esteem. The stress of trying to meet the unrealistic standards found on social media makes this complex worse, ultimately damaging the user's mental health and overall well-being (Amani et al., 2024; American Psychological Association, n.d.; Uniyal et al., 2023).

Rationale and Objective of the Study

There is a lot of awareness regarding the ill effects of social media usage and the impact it has on the mental health of users. Previous studies mostly focused on correlational relationships between social media use and Fear of Missing Out or FoMO and self-esteem, with very few exploring how these variables interact together. Additionally, there is not much clarity regarding the role of FoMO in self-evaluative processes. This gives space for exploring whether FoMO has any role in the development of inferiority complex. Previous Indian researches explored digital addiction, or the effect of social media on mental health, mostly on adolescents population, with very few on emerging adults. Based on these gaps, the rationale of this research is to determine if Fear of Missing out serves as a psychological bridge between social media use and the development of inferiority complex. The objective of this paper was to study the relationship between social media use, fear of missing out and inferiority complex and to explore if FoMO plays a mediating role in adults aged 18-30 years.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: There will be no significant association between Social media use and Fear of missing out.
- *H2*: There will be no significant association between Fear of missing out and Inferiority Complex.
- *H3*: There will be no significant association between Social media use and Inferiority Complex.
- *H4*: Fear of missing out will not mediate the relationship between Social media use and Inferiority Complex.

Method

Research Design and Participants

The present study utilised a quantitative, cross-sectional, correlational research design to explore associations between Social Media Use, Fear of Missing Out and Inferiority Complex. A convenience sampling technique was used. The final sample consisted of 212 respondents, which included 135 females (63.7%) and 77 males (36.3%). The inclusion criteria required the respondents between the ages 18 to 30 with the ability to read and understand English, use social media for at least an hour and provide informed consent. Respondents currently

under any psychological medications or who refused to provide informed consent were excluded from the study.

Measures

Data was collected using standardised psychological measures along with social demographic details, which included respondents' patterns of social media use (active, passive, balanced).

Social Media Use Scale-SMUS (Tuck & Thompson, 2024): SMUS is a 17-item 9-point Likert scale, which measures the frequency of interaction in certain social media behaviours across four domains: image-based, comparison-based, belief-based and consumption-based use. Respondents rated each item on a scale (1 = *Never* to 9 = *Hourly or more*). The interpretation of the scores is based on the subscale total, each signifying the kind of social media use an individual generally engages in. The SMUS has good reliability with Cronbach's $\alpha = .84$ for the domain belief-based, $\alpha = .81$ for image-based, $\alpha = .80$ for consumption-based, and $\alpha = .77$ for comparison-based.

Fear of Missing Out Scale-FoMOS (Przybylski et al., 2013): The FoMOS is a 10-item self-report measure used to assess the degree to which an individual fears missing out on events involving others, such as friends and using social media to stay in touch. Respondents rated statements on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *Not at all true of me* to 5 = *Extremely true of me*). Higher scores demonstrate higher FoMO. The scale shows high internal consistency.

COMPIN-10 (Čekrljija et al., 2025): Inferiority Complex was assessed using the 10-item COMPIN scale, a short version of the original 40-item scale. Respondents responded to statements on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *Completely incorrect* to 5 = *Completely correct*). All the items are positively scored, with higher scores representing higher feelings of inferiority and individuals' feelings of low worth about themselves in general. The COMPIN-10 shows robust unidimensional structure, high reliability $\alpha = .82$.90 across 9 countries.

Procedure

Respondents were approached through social media platforms, offline university networks, and personal contacts. Paper-based responses taken offline were systematically digitised for statistical analysis. Participation was strictly voluntary, and all respondents were provided with informed consent forms before the administration of the questionnaires. The survey was administered in a fixed sequence to prevent priming effects: socio-demographic details were collected first, followed sequentially by the SMUS, FoMOS, and COMPIN-10.

Results

IBM SPSS statistics was used to analyse the data taken from 212 respondents.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics (Mean, SD) and Correlation of Respondents on the Measures of the Four Subscales of Social Media Use Scale, Fear of Missing Out Scale and COMPIN-10

Variable	Mean	SD	Consumption-based SMUS	Image-based SMUS	Comparison-based SMUS	Belief-based SMUS	Fear of Missing Out (FoMO)
Consumption-based SMUS	18.78	7.70	-				
Image-based SMUS	10.58	4.71	.50**	-			
Comparison-based SMUS	7.67	4.14	.67**	.31**	-		
Belief-based SMUS	6.34	3.00	.43**	.42**	.29**	-	
Fear of Missing Out (FoMO)	21.25	6.98	.36**	.32**	.44**	.28**	-
Inferiority Complex (COMPIN-10)	26.30	9.51	.21*	.11	.32**	.07	.38**

Note. $N = 212$, SMUS- social media use scale, * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$

Descriptive statistics and correlation for the variables are presented in Table 1. The analysis showed that all the subscales of SMUS positively correlated with FoMO, with comparison-based SMUS showing strong correlation ($r = .44, p < .01$). Based on this hypothesis 1 was rejected. There was a strong positive correlation of FoMO with Inferiority Complex ($r = .38, p < .01$, leading to rejection of hypothesis 2. Finally, both Comparison-based ($r = .32, p < .01$) and Consumption-based ($r = .21, p < .01$) social media use were significantly correlated with Inferiority complex, rejecting

hypothesis 3.

Independent sample t-tests showed there were no significant differences between males and females regarding total Social Media Use Scale (SMUS) scores ($p = .327$), Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) ($p = .248$), or Inferiority Complex ($p = .171$). However, a significant negative correlation was observed between comparison-based SMUS and age ($r = -.21$), indicating that comparative social media use decreases as individuals mature.

Table 2

One-Way ANOVA of Inferiority Complex Across Social Media Usage Patterns

Variable	Active	Passive	Balanced	F(2, 209)	p
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)		
Inferiority Complex	24.54 (8.95)	28.01 (9.47)	24.48 (9.42)	3.71	.026*

Note. $N = 212$. $M =$ Mean; $SD =$ Standard Deviation. $p < .05$. Post-hoc comparisons using the Bonferroni correction indicated that Passive users reported significantly higher Inferiority Complex scores than Balanced users ($p = .039$).

Table 2 shows One-way ANOVA, conducted to explore if specific pattern of social media use (active, passive, balanced) had an impact on inferiority complex. The results showed a statistically significant difference between these groups, $F(2, 209) = 3.71, p = .026$. Post-hoc

tests using the Bonferroni criterion confirmed that Passive users have significantly higher Inferiority Complex scores than Balanced users ($p = .039$).

Table 3

Mediation Analyses Depicting Partial Mediation Effect of FoMO on Inferiority Complex

Path	Coefficient (b)	SE	t	p	95% CI
Comparison SMUS \rightarrow FoMO (Path a)	.75***	.10	7.12	< .001	[.54, .95]
FoMO \rightarrow Inferiority complex (Path b)	.40***	.10	4.18	< .001	[.21, .59]
Total effect (c)	.73***	.15	4.85	< .001	[.43, 1.03]
Direct effect (c')	.43**	.16	2.68	.008	[.11, .75]
Indirect effect (ab)	.30	.09	-	-	[.14, .47]

Note. $N = 212$. Mediator = FOMO. Dependent Variable = Inferiority Complex (COMPIN). Unstandardized coefficients are reported. CI = Bias-corrected bootstrap confidence interval based on 5,000 samples. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$

To test hypothesis 4, a simple mediation analysis was conducted using Hayes' PROCESS macro (model 4) to explore whether FoMO acts as a mediator between comparison-based SMUS and Inferiority Complex. As shown in Table 3, Comparison-based use significantly predicted inferiority complex (Total effect = 0.73, $p < .001$). When FoMO was controlled, Comparison-based use continued to directly predict inferiority complex (Direct effect = 0.43, $p = .008$). Additionally, the indirect effect through FoMO was also significant (Effect = 0.30, 95% CI [0.14, 0.47]). Because the confidence interval did not include zero, this shows complementary partial mediation, leading to the rejection of Hypothesis 4.

Interestingly, an exploratory analysis was conducted using the Total SMUS scores, which revealed full mediation. This indicates that overall screen time only leads to an inferiority complex if it first triggers FoMO.

Figure 1

*Statistical Path Diagram Depicting the Partial Mediation of Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) in the Relationship between Comparison-based Social Media Use and Inferiority Complex. Unstandardized coefficients are presented. The total effect (Path c) is reported in parentheses. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$*

Discussion

The objective of this study was to explore the relationship between Social media use, Fear of Missing Out and development of Inferiority Complex and whether FoMO acts as a mediator between social media use and inferiority complex. The statistical analysis rejects all the null hypotheses, helping to understand how social media use affect young adults.

The findings show a strong emotional-behavioural connection that consuming the content on social media and comparing oneself to others increases the anxiety of missing out. Young adults use social media to avoid the feelings of FoMO, but constantly viewing their peers 'edited' updates, they may feel that they are missing out on many experiences, eventually leading to more FoMO and a harmful endless loop. This supports a study done by Gupta (2024) which states that FoMO acts as a psychological driver that forces individuals to check their phones constantly. Furthermore, the data proves that FoMO is not just a temporary feeling. When individuals constantly feel that they are excluded online, they may internalise this feeling as personal failure. Over time, this affects the self-esteem and can develop into a lasting inferiority complex.

The ANOVA results indicate that just spending time online is not the main problem but the way individuals engage in social media use is what matters. Passive scrolling when combined with upward comparison- comparing one's life to others who are perceived to be more successful or have it better- creates a highly toxic environment mentally. This aligns with Feinstein et al. (2013) who highlighted that constant negative online comparison acts as a primary risk factor for negative rumination.

Mediation analysis contributed to the most significant finding that the partial mediation of comparison-based social media use acts as a double threat to the mental well-being of young adults. Firstly, indirect harm caused by comparing one's everyday life to the digital highlights of others causes FoMO, which eventually lowers self-worth. This is in line with Wang et al. (2025) who established that upward comparison makes it impossible for individuals to satisfy their basic psychological needs, and this makes FoMO worse. Secondly, the immediate harm caused by the comparison of one's real life to the perfect and photo-shopped life of another person results in mental harm, even to the person who does not experience FoMO. As Soomro et al. (2017) highlighted, the majority of online comparisons are upward, leading to a drop in self-esteem.

In contrast, the full mediation using total social media use scores established that total screen time does not directly affect self-esteem but only leads to inferiority complex if FoMO is triggered. If individuals are constantly online, but do not experience any FoMO, then they do not develop inferiority complex. This is supported by a study done by Reer et al. (2019) which proposed that FoMO and comparison behaviours serve as psychological bridges connecting excessive social media use to mental health problems.

There was no significant differences found between genders in Fears of Missing Out. This suggests that the pressure to create a perfect online persona and the fear or social exclusion are universal struggles faced by both men and women equally. It was also found that comparison-based social media use decreases with age. Because social comparison and FoMO are the causes of psychological distress, simply taking a digital detox will not be a useful solution. Instead, interventions should focus on cognitive behavioural tools and methods such as the FoMO-R approach by Alutaybi et al. (2020)

which teaches social media users to regulate their emotions and manage their online comparisons, and represents a more practical way to support and enhance digital resilience.

Conclusion

This study contributes to understanding that the total time spent online does not lead to inferiority complex but rather how young adults engage in social media use such as passive scrolling and upward comparison. The most critical finding is that Fear of Missing Out (FoMO) plays a mediating role, bridging social media use and inferiority complex. Excessive use of social media affects self-esteem primarily when the fear of missing out is triggered. Additionally, comparison-based social media use acts as a double threat by causing FoMO, and if not that, then affecting self-esteem through watching edited and fabricated online updates of others. As a result, therapeutic interventions must be updated. Since digital distress is driven by comparison and FoMO, suggesting unrealistic digital detoxes will be ineffective. Clinicians should instead prioritize cognitive-behavioural strategies and digital literacy programs-such as the FoMO-R method-to equip young adults with the emotional regulation skills needed to navigate the digital world resiliently.

Limitations and Future Studies

Although this study has provided significant insights, there are a few limitations to the study. The cross-sectional design cannot establish cause and effect, and the use of self-report measures is likely to be influenced by social desirability bias. Additionally, the sample size ($N= 212$) was heavily skewed toward female participants (63.7%), which may limit how well these findings apply to all young adults.

Future research could focus on using longitudinal designs to clarify the exact chronological sequence of how online comparison triggers FoMO and leads to an inferiority complex.

Additionally, qualitative methods, such as semi-structured interviews, could help identify specific types of content-like professional milestones on LinkedIn or idealized travel photos on Instagram-that most strongly provoke these psychological problems.

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